

Evolution in Agriculture Due to Digitalisation in India with Special Reference to Previous Five Years

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Abstract

The Indian agriculture sector accounts for 80% of India’s Gross Domestic Product and employs 50% of the country’s work force. India, directly and indirectly, depends on agriculture. This paper has the main objective of studying evolution, growth in the agricultural sector due to the introduction of technology in the last five years. Critical analysis of the available information is the main content of the paper. The data collected as been used to provide suggestions and recommendations for the future growth of the sector.

Keywords: Evolution, Technology, Gross Domestic Product, Growth.

Introduction of Agriculture in India

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy. Around 59% population of India depends on Agriculture. India is the second worldwide in farm output. India is the leading producer of jute, pulses. The second-largest producer of wheat, paddy, fruits, vegetables. The economic contribution of agriculture to India’s GDP is steadily declining with the country’s broad-based economic growth. India exported \$39 billion worth of agriculture products in 2013. In 2013 India became seventh-largest agriculture exporter world-wide. Most of its agricultural exports serves other nation than developed nations.

Evolution of Agriculture in India

Indian agriculture began by 9000 BCE in north-west India as a result of the early cultivation of plants and the domestication of crops and animals. The harvest have been reaped twice in a year during double monsoon.

The 1950s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stagnation in agriculture • Low growth in crop and grain production. (0.4 & 0.1%p.a) • Food cereal production of 59.2mt in 1952-53 with a yield of 579.8kg
1960-1980	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pioneering work of agriculture and scientist and efforts of farmers led to the Green Revolution. • High Yield Variety (HYV) of seeds, increased use of fertilizers. Hence it resulted to produce more than before.
1980-2000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding grain production. • Economic reforms help in a greater encouragement of exports. • India came out as a net exporter of agricultural products. • Increase in population and increase income growth.
2000 onwards	<p>MNC players brought in better technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rise in institutional credit for agriculture. • The government launched NFSM (National Food Security Mission) to increase the production of commodities. • Schemes like National Horticulture Mission (NHM) and Bringing Green Revolution in Eastern India (BRED) helped achieve record production. • Commodity exchanges helped in the fair pricing of commodities.

Objectives

1. To Study the implementation of technology in agriculture in India.
2. To compare the use of technology in the past and the present.
3. To analyze the growth of agriculture in India after the introduction of technology.

Sources of Information

1. The data had been collected with the help of a secondary source.
2. Published and unpublished work was used to collect the information. Data had been taken from government related websites.

Traditional Agriculture in India

British Agricultural Revolution is nothing but a dramatic increase in agricultural productivity in between 17th and 19th century. This “Revolution” consisted of a variety of improvements to agricultural methods, which took place more or less impact. Farmers developed modern methods such as crop rotation, began cultivating land that had been marshy or forested, and planted new crops such as the turnip etc. The technology of agriculture has continued to be changing over the years. Plows and other farming was implemented. The mechanical combine harvester – The machine that harvests grain – was invented in the 1830s. Initially tractors were of steam-powered engines designed to haul agriculture equipment and were too expensive for most farmers to afford.

In the previous century farming methods changed a lot. Hybrids helps in improving the planting and often produce plants and fruits that are hardier and more uniform. Hybrid seeds contributed to the increased agriculture output of the second half of the 20th century.

The changes have not all come quietly. The usage of more of chemical pesticides and fertilizers on farms which will get affected to human health. To give awareness government implemented some new rules and regulations.

Limitations of Traditional Agriculture

1. Traditional farming does not use more insecticides hence the plants are at more risk of suffering diseases.
2. The traditional farming wasn't very efficient as no soil enrichment products were used, and no modern technologies either.
3. Due to increase in the cost of traditional farming there is more unreliability and less efficiency.
4. Farmers in traditional farming have to spend. It takes a long time to harvest hence being.
5. One of the main dis-advantage of traditional farming is Low output, i.e., fewer crops can be taken out.

Modern Agriculture in India

Digital agriculture refers to tools that digitally collect, store, analyze, and share electronic data and information along the agricultural value chain. Sometimes known as “smart farming” or “e-agriculture,” Digital agriculture includes development in agriculture. Therefore, on-farm technologies, like yield mapping, GPS guidance systems, and variable-rate application, fall under the domain of precision agriculture and digital agriculture. Digital technologies involved in e-commerce platforms, e-extension services, warehouse receipt systems, time the umbrella of digital agriculture but not precision agriculture.

Technologies for Agricultural Development

Pre & Post Harvesting Technology

- **Pre-harvest Activities:** Selection of crop and its variety for cultivation. Use of high-quality seeds and healthy saplings. Treatment of seeds before sowing. Proper preparation of soil for sowing. Sowing the seeds, too early or too late results in poor crop yield. Plants have been protected from diseases and harmful insects.
- **Time of Harvesting:** Expected time of maturity or ripening. The expected time gap between production and utilization. Available modes of packing and storage. The case of food grains, moisture content of the grain should also being considered.

Energy-Saving Technology

Developing renewable energy technology. Adopting a smarter lifestyle.

Environment Protection Technology

Saving the environment with technology developing renewable energy technology. One of the most significant ways to contribute to saving the environment is to sustain, generate and utilise the available energy resources.

Information and Communication Technology

It is an expandable term for information technology that stresses the role of unified communication and the integration of tele-communications (telephone lines and wireless signals) and computers, as well as necessary enterprise software, middleware, storage, and audio-visual systems, that enable to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information.

GIS and RS Technology

A GIS (Geographic Information System)

A GIS is a computer-based tool for mapping and analysing features and events on earth. It integrates common database operations, such as query and statistical analysis, with maps.

RS (Remote Sensing)

Remote sensing is nothing but collection of data regarding an object phenomenon without any physical contact with the objective.

Internet/Intranet Technology

Internet

The internet is a global network that establishes a connection and provides transmission between various computers. It uses both wired and wireless modes of communication to send and receive any information such as data, audio, video, etcetera. Here, data travels through “fibre optic cables”, which are owned by telephone companies. The initial idea of the internet was introduced by the US Defence Organization ARPA (Advanced Research Project Agency) in the late 1960s.

Intranet

An intranet is a part of the Internet that is privately owned by an organisation. It connects all the computers together and provides access to files and folders within that specific network. It has a firewall surrounding the system to avoid the unauthorized user from accessing the network. Only authorized users have permission to access the network.

AG-Apps Classification

- ID Apps: For identification purpose (Weeds, insects, etc.)
- ECON Apps: For checking grain prices, market evolutions, News, and Finances.
- SCOUT Apps: For Scouting purposes or geo-positioning (Soil sampling, Soil types, etc.)
- GUIDE Apps: For diagnosing crop production issues in the field, related to field guides.
- GAG Apps: GAG (General Ag-Apps) For general use, management, weather-related, magazines, and more.
- AGRI-Apps: It is an online farming marketplace bringing Kisan, farming input/output, government service on an online platform.
- IFFCO KISAN APP: Iffco Kisan is the best app in out of almost agricultural apps for Kisan. It is a small android app in terms of memory with an easy interface to use.

Finding and Interpretation

Following is the table showing the agricultural growth rate from the year 2010-2019

SL. No	Year	Agriculture Rate in Percentage
1	2010	8.6%
2	2011	5.0%
3	2012	1.5%
4	2013	5.6%
5	2014	-0.2%
6	2015	0.7%
7	2016	4.9%
8	2017	2.1%
9	2018	2.9%
10	2019	3.96%

Agri-Contribution to GDP Declining

GDP Rate From 2005 - 2012

GDP Rate From 2014 - 2019

Conclusion

The Proper usage of technology has resulted in massive agricultural output in India. When compared to a foreign country, India does not use technology to the fullest extent as the rural population is majorly involved in agriculture in India. For maximum implementation in technology to the people involved in agriculture should be accurately educated regarding the availability of information and technology. Necessary training should also be given in this regard. Hence it can be concluded that India has a bright future in the agriculture sector if traditional agriculture is merged with modern agricultural techniques.

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